

THE ROLE OF MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES*S. Muradova¹, M. Sattorova²**Abstract:*

This article presents superiority of modern teaching methods and approaches rather than traditional system of education and how to use of them in teaching foreign language.

Key words: methods, approach, new devices, pedagogy, learning process, cooperative learning, suggestopedia

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It is obvious that, teaching is based on two major components: teaching and receiving information. With reference to a foreign language lesson, the project is specially organized by the teacher and independently carried out by students' complex actions, and finished with a creation of a product. At present time teaching, a foreign language focuses on aims of teaching: communicative, educational, developing and bringing up goals. Among these purposes, we can say communicative aspirations takes in main part. Other aims are used to cover the tasks in communicative aim with some typical features. Teaching foreign language is also developing swiftly and according to the demand of time it applies modern methods, pedagogical technologies, interactive methods and their multimedia, monopedia by showing their effective results. The researchers consider that the teaching would be highly effective if the teacher start to use the recent multimedia technologies like usage of computers extensively or some modifications in the conventional mode of teaching. The use of computers may be very well practiced in the environment where the use of such technology is highly possible, but there must be some sort of innovation which can also be practiced in an environment where such use of technology is on its way to growth. We analyzed some examples in some cases, which show how to achieve the several aims with the help of new intensive methods and modern technologies such as expanding student's vocabulary basement, fixing investigated lexical and grammatical material at the lesson. There is one crucial target aims, which deals with obtaining the above mentioned.

Using modern methods, approaches and new technologies help teaching foreign language effectively and intensively. There are: interactive method, communicative method, suggestopedia method, hyponomedia method, community language learning method and etc. We analyze some important points of these methods in teaching foreign languages with the help of some examples. As we know, communication is vital aspect of teaching foreign language. Because it devotes to exchange information. Similarly, it reveals learners mental abilities during the lesson. The main points of this

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communicative method are teaching language in communication, analyzing language materials, teaching learners how to communicate with each other's, teaching language by correcting and discussing errors. The main idea of this method is avoiding traditional style of teaching. Learners' communication can be seen in giving opinion, retelling, and receiving information.

Another effective method is suggestopedia. Bulgarian scientist Georgiy Lozanov introduced Suggestopedia. It aimed at letting out learner's inner talents which is hidden. The language is taught by influencing the learners' state of mind. More attention is given to the learner's memory. According to the Lozanov's method, the foreign language can be taught within thirty days in ten stages. In one day by four hours of teaching, it lasts six days. He also subdivided listening into the dialogues, imitation the dialogues, making up the new dialogues and the numbers of learners should be twelve in class but not more.

On the other hand, we cannot imagine our life without technologies. Our daily routine, jobs are connected with them as well. So what is the essential role of innovative technology in teaching foreign language? Showing one of the advantageous technologies, we can include multimedia to create a context to teach English successfully if we speak about necessity of multimedia technology, by the way we will get rid of teaching in traditional ways. Because of modern technology, we can teach with the help of video, audio materials. During the lesson, it is very efficient way in teaching and sending information to students easily. It is stated that multimedia technology has various benefits in promoting activities and abilities of students and sufficient teaching process during the lesson. One of the multimedia technologies is internet, which has bewitched the increase of English through the world. Because of this fact, we can get more and more details, information and factual events from the social net. Nowadays, majority of teachers use multimedia technology as a means of giving more colorful lectures and also other subjects some are practical for testing and distance education and sometimes for teaching other spheres such as business, law, medicine and others.

There are several causes why all teachers and learners must be aware of using modern technologies. Such as, there are many modern methods and approaches such as project-based learning and task-based learning etc. According to time requirement during the lessons, they have to use projector, TV or laptops. In project-based learning teacher give tasks learners or students by utilizing innovations in order to present or submit their tasks in ways of presentation, video, album, poster etc.

Technology is also changing the classroom environment. The classrooms at present time all sorts are convenient for students and teachers. For instance, tablet PCs, compact computers that allow you to write notes directly onto the screen with a special pen, replace the archaic projector. With the tablet technology allow professors to make notes on charts and spreadsheets and send them directly to their students' PCs and he will get feedback from each student.

From the above, we can make out that the modern methods, approaches and communication technology has made many innovations in the field of teaching and also made a drastic change from the old paradigm of teaching and learning. In the new paradigm of learning, the role of student is more important than teachers. The concepts of paperless and pen less classroom are a bit emerging as an alternative to the old teaching learning method. Nowadays there is democratization of knowledge and the role of the teacher is changing to that

of facilitator. We need to have interactive teaching and this changing role of education is inevitable with the introduction of multimedia technology. The scholars believe that the main objective of teaching is transferring the information and knowledge to the minds of the students. In any method using computers and multimedia are also innovative if they influence the aims of teaching effectively. As we know among all foreign languages the most widely spread and used language is English. English is becoming more and more interactive with the help of innovative teaching methods and strategies. When it comes to the perception of interactivity, it is ordinary for any English lessons in so far as its principal aim is to improve the learners' ability to communicate in English connecting with real life situations. There are different types of interactive methods that have specific affectivity in teaching English language, such as roleplaying, brainstorming, discussion, case study, debates, and others. It is stated that there are a number of classifications of interactive methods. According to Arutyunov he divided them into two groups: 1) problem-based learning, including practical drills, discussions, conferences; 2) game-based learning: for instance, business games, projects, role-playing, simulation exercises which develop thinking capability and motivation, the instructions and others.

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